

SPIRITUAL EXPLORATION IN THE COSMOS - UNDERSTANDING VOLITION
IN SPIRITISM AND CONSCIENIOLOGY

EXPLORAÇÃO ESPIRITUAL NO COSMOS – COMPREENDENDO A
VOLIÇÃO NO ESPIRITISMO E NA CONSCIENCIOLÓGIA

Edenilson Brandl

Cognitive-Behavioral Therapist, English Professor, Author, Master's Student in
Genetics, Specialist in Business Intelligence and Project Management,
Bachelor's Degree in Production Engineering, Degree in Pedagogy.
engbrandl@yahoo.com.br

Abstract:

This comprehensive exploration delves into the metaphysical concepts of levitation, volition, and consciousness within the frameworks of Spiritism and Conscientiology. Rooted in the teachings of Allan Kardec and Waldo Vieira, these spiritual traditions propose the existence of phenomena such as levitation, where spirits or consciousness defy gravitational forces, and volition, allowing autonomous movement in and beyond the cosmic domain. The article critically examines the theoretical foundations, explores reported cases, and contemplates the potential implications of these phenomena within the vastness of outer space. Bridging the realms of spiritual philosophy and scientific inquiry, the discussion navigates through logical, methodological, and ethical challenges, encouraging an interdisciplinary dialogue. By reflecting on alternative perspectives and external criticisms, the article seeks to foster a nuanced understanding of volition, consciousness, and their place in both the metaphysical and empirical realms. The call for further research and contemplation underscores the ongoing nature of this inquiry, aiming to enrich our comprehension of the intricate intersections between spirituality, science, and cosmic exploration.

Keywords: Volition, Consciousness, Spiritism, Conscientiology, Metaphysical phenomena, Levitation, Cosmic exploration, Spiritual philosophy, Allan Kardec, Waldo Vieira.

Abstrakt:

Esta exploração abrangente investiga os conceitos metafísicos de levitação, volição e consciência dentro das estruturas do Espiritismo e da Conscienciologia. Enraizadas nos ensinamentos de Allan Kardec e Waldo Vieira, estas tradições espirituais propõem a existência de fenômenos como a levitação, onde os espíritos ou a consciência desafiam as forças gravitacionais, e a volição, permitindo o movimento autónomo dentro e fora do domínio cósmico. O artigo examina criticamente os fundamentos teóricos, explora casos relatados e contempla as implicações potenciais desses fenômenos na vastidão do espaço sideral. Unindo os domínios da filosofia espiritual e da investigação científica, a discussão navega por desafios lógicos, metodológicos e éticos, incentivando um diálogo interdisciplinar. Ao refletir sobre perspectivas alternativas e críticas externas, o artigo procura promover uma compreensão diferenciada da volição, da consciência e do seu lugar tanto no domínio metafísico como no empírico. O apelo a mais investigação e contemplação sublinha a natureza contínua desta investigação, com o objetivo de enriquecer a nossa compreensão das intrincadas interseções entre espiritualidade, ciência e exploração cósmica.

Palavras-chave: Volição, Consciência, Espiritismo, Conscienciologia, Fenômenos Metafísicos, Levitação, Exploração Cósmica, Filosofia Espiritual, Allan Kardec, Waldo Vieira.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the exploration of spiritual doctrines and metaphysical phenomena, Spiritism and Conscientiology stand as distinct yet interconnected frameworks that delve into the nature of consciousness, volition, and levitation. Founded by Allan Kardec in the 19th century, Spiritism posits the ethereal movement of spirits in spiritual planes, linking levitation to the separation of the spiritual body from the physical during specific spiritual experiences. On the other hand, Conscientiology, a more contemporary discipline introduced by Waldo Vieira, extends the scope beyond traditional spiritualism, associating levitation with the mobility of consciousness itself. Both traditions share a fundamental tenet—the

malleability and transcendence of consciousness beyond the confines of the physical body.

This article embarks on a comprehensive exploration of volition, or autonomous movement, within the contexts of Spiritism and Conscientiology, offering a nuanced examination at the intersection of spiritual philosophy and metaphysical phenomena. We delve into the theoretical foundations, drawing from seminal texts such as Allan Kardec's "The Spirits' Book" and Waldo Vieira's "Projectiology." Our inquiry extends to reported cases of out-of-body experiences and volition, prompting critical reflections on the potential interplay between metaphysical claims and empirical scrutiny.

As humanity advances its understanding of the cosmos through scientific inquiry, the juxtaposition of spiritual doctrines with cosmic realities poses both a philosophical and scientific challenge. The prospect of spirits or consciousness navigating the spatial void through volition prompts a critical examination of the intersection between spiritual beliefs and the laws governing the universe. This exploration is motivated by a desire to bridge the gap between the esoteric and the empirical, fostering a comprehensive dialogue that enriches our understanding of both the spiritual and astronomical dimensions. By engaging with the concept of volition in the context of space, this inquiry aims to unravel the potential synergies and conflicts between spiritual philosophies and the scientific principles that govern celestial bodies and their interactions.

2. DEVELOPMENT

Levitation, as conceptualized in both Spiritism and Conscientiology, represents a phenomenon within the metaphysical frameworks of these spiritual traditions. In Spiritism, a doctrine founded by Allan Kardec in the 19th century, levitation is often understood as the purported ability of spirits or entities to defy gravitational forces and move through space independently of physical constraints. This phenomenon is intricately linked to the Spiritist belief in the separation of the spiritual body, or perispirit, from the physical body during certain spiritual experiences. Conscientiology, on the other hand, a more recent philosophical and multidisciplinary approach founded by Waldo Vieira, extends the exploration of levitation to a broader examination of consciousness beyond

the limits of traditional spiritualism. Within the Conscientiological framework, levitation is considered a potential manifestation of the consciousness outside the corporeal boundaries, encompassing experiences that transcend conventional notions of spatial limitations.

The concept of levitation in both Spiritism and Conscientiology underscores a fundamental tenet of these doctrines—the malleability and transcendence of consciousness beyond the confines of the physical body. While Spiritism attributes levitation to the ethereal movement of spirits in spiritual planes, Conscientiology expands the scope, associating it with the mobility of consciousness itself. In both paradigms, levitation is intimately tied to the separation of the spiritual or conscious essence from the physical vessel, suggesting a dynamic interplay between the metaphysical and physical realms. As these traditions provide distinct lenses through which to examine the phenomenon, the exploration of levitation serves as a gateway to understanding their perspectives on the nature of consciousness, its autonomy, and its potential interactions with the cosmos.

The exploration of volition, or the act of volitating, within the frameworks of Spiritism and Conscientiology represents an intriguing intersection of spiritual philosophy and metaphysical phenomena. In Spiritism, a doctrine codified by Allan Kardec in the 19th century, volitation is considered a form of movement achieved by discarnate spirits independently of physical constraints. This phenomenon is intricately linked to the understanding of the perispirit, a semi-material envelope that, according to Spiritist teachings, connects the spirit to the corporeal body. Conscientiology, a more contemporary discipline developed by Waldo Vieira, expands on these concepts, introducing the idea of consciential energies and proposing a more comprehensive exploration of consciousness. Within this context, volitation extends beyond simple locomotion, becoming an avenue for consciousness to navigate space and explore dimensions beyond the terrestrial realm. These perspectives lay the groundwork for a nuanced examination of how the ethereal nature of volitation aligns with the cosmic expanse.

The motivation to delve into the exploration of volition in the cosmic realm emanates from a quest to comprehend the potential interplay between metaphysical phenomena and the vastness of outer space. As humanity

continues to advance its understanding of the cosmos through scientific inquiry, the juxtaposition of spiritual doctrines with cosmic realities poses both a philosophical and scientific challenge. The prospect of spirits navigating the spatial void through volitation prompts a critical examination of the intersection between spiritual beliefs and the laws governing the universe. This exploration is motivated by a desire to bridge the gap between the esoteric and the empirical, fostering a comprehensive dialogue that enriches our understanding of both the spiritual and astronomical dimensions. By engaging with the concept of volitation in the context of space, this inquiry aims to unravel the potential synergies and conflicts between spiritual philosophies and the scientific principles that govern celestial bodies and their interactions.

The theoretical foundations of both Spiritism and Conscienciology revolve around the existence of the spirit as a distinct entity with unique capacities. In Spiritism, influenced by the works of Allan Kardec, the concept of the spirit as an immortal and evolving entity is central. The doctrine posits that the spirit undergoes successive incarnations, accumulating experiences to achieve moral and intellectual progress. The perispirit, a semi-material body, serves as the intermediary between the spirit and the physical body, allowing for communication and interaction with the material world. Spiritism's theoretical framework acknowledges the spirit's capacity for volition and movement, attributing to it a degree of autonomy that extends beyond the confines of the physical body. This acknowledgment lays the groundwork for the exploration of phenomena such as volitation, where the spirit is believed to navigate space independently of corporeal limitations.

Conscienciology, as developed by Waldo Vieira, extends the theoretical underpinnings of Spiritism by introducing the concept of consciencial energies and emphasizing the multidimensional nature of consciousness. According to Conscienciology, the spirit, or consciousness, is not confined to a single incarnation but exists as part of a larger evolutionary scheme spanning multiple lifetimes and dimensions. Conscienciological theories propose that consciousness can manifest in different bodies and environments, expressing a spectrum of capabilities beyond the traditional understanding of the spirit. The concept of consciencial energies implies that consciousness has a dynamic nature, capable of influencing and interacting with its surroundings, including

the spatial dimensions explored during phenomena like volition. These theoretical frameworks collectively offer insights into the nature of the spirit and its purported capacities, forming the basis for the examination of metaphysical phenomena within the realms of Spiritism and Conscienciology.

The exploration of volition and related phenomena within the context of Spiritism and Conscienciology draws heavily from foundational texts that have shaped the understanding of these spiritual doctrines. In the realm of Spiritism, "The Spirits' Book," compiled by Allan Kardec in the mid-19th century, serves as a cornerstone text. This seminal work provides a systematic inquiry into the nature of spirits, their interactions with the material world, and the principles governing phenomena such as volition. Kardec's meticulous examination of mediumistic communications and spirit teachings laid the groundwork for the conceptualization of the spirit's capabilities, including the ability to transcend physical boundaries through volition.

In the realm of Conscienciology, Waldo Vieira's "Projectiology: A Panorama of Experiences of the Consciousness Outside the Human Body" stands out as a fundamental text. Vieira's work explores the out-of-body experience (OBE) and its implications for understanding the multidimensional nature of consciousness. The book delves into the dynamics of consciousness beyond the corporeal confines, offering insights into how consciousness, or the spirit, can navigate different dimensions. Vieira's systematic approach and empirical observations contribute to the theoretical foundations that underpin the exploration of volition and spatial phenomena within the framework of Conscienciology. These foundational texts provide the intellectual scaffolding for the examination of volition, guiding the inquiry into the spiritual and metaphysical dimensions of these phenomena.

The understanding of the nature of volition within the traditions of Spiritism and Conscienciology involves a nuanced exploration of the spirit's relationship with the physical and metaphysical realms. In Spiritism, the nature of volition is intricately connected to the concept of the perispirit, an ethereal body that mediates the interaction between the spirit and the physical body. Spiritist teachings propose that volition is an inherent capacity of the spirit, allowing it to move independently of the physical body during out-of-body experiences or mediumistic phenomena. The nature of volition in Spiritism

implies a form of locomotion that transcends gravitational constraints, suggesting a dynamic interaction between the spirit and its environment that goes beyond the laws governing the material world.

Conscienciology expands on this understanding by introducing the concept of consciential energies, framing volition as a manifestation of the consciousness's dynamic influence on its surroundings. According to Conscienciological principles, volition is not merely a mode of movement but an expression of consciousness interacting with multidimensional realities. The nature of volition in Conscienciology implies a broader spectrum of capabilities, where the consciousness can navigate not only physical space but also different dimensions and states of existence. This conceptualization aligns with the idea that volition represents a fundamental aspect of consciousness, shaping the nature of spiritual experiences within the framework of Conscienciology. The nuanced perspectives within these traditions contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the nature of volition, bridging the metaphysical and empirical realms in the exploration of consciousness and its capacities.

The exploration of volition within the spiritual context often involves the examination of anecdotal reports and documented cases that purport to exemplify the phenomenon. In the realm of Spiritism, numerous accounts of individuals experiencing out-of-body experiences (OBEs) and volition have been recorded through mediumistic communications and personal testimonies. These narratives frequently describe instances where individuals, in a state of altered consciousness, claim to have moved beyond the confines of their physical bodies, navigating through space and interacting with non-physical entities. While these reports are crucial for understanding the subjective experiences associated with volition, the scientific scrutiny of such cases remains a challenge, as the nature of spiritual phenomena often eludes conventional empirical verification.

Conscienciology contributes to the exploration of volition through the systematic study of out-of-body experiences and consciousness dynamics. Reported cases within Conscienciology literature often involve individuals describing intentional and controlled movements of their consciousness outside the body, suggesting a form of volition that extends beyond the physical

constraints. These cases, documented through the lens of Conscienciological research, aim to provide a more systematic and rigorous approach to the study of volition, incorporating methodologies such as self-experimentation and multidimensional assessments. While these cases offer intriguing insights into the potential capabilities of consciousness, the interpretation of such reports requires a balanced consideration of subjective experiences and the challenges associated with scientifically validating phenomena that transcend the conventional boundaries of materialistic inquiry.

Contemplating how volition fits within the context of the cosmic environment involves a nuanced consideration of the physical laws governing space and the purported metaphysical capabilities of consciousness. In the absence of a gravitational field or atmospheric constraints in outer space, traditional concepts of movement and navigation lose their terrestrial parameters. From a scientific standpoint, the idea of volition in space raises intriguing questions regarding the potential interaction between consciousness and the cosmic backdrop. It prompts reflection on whether, in the absence of gravitational forces as we understand them, consciousness could navigate space independently, challenging the conventional understanding of propulsion and locomotion. The juxtaposition of spiritual concepts like volition with the vast, seemingly boundless expanses of space underscores the interdisciplinary nature of this inquiry, necessitating a nuanced dialogue between spiritual philosophy and the laws of physics.

Considering the cosmic environment within the framework of volition also invites contemplation on the potential characteristics of consciousness navigating space. The vacuum of space, with its absence of air resistance and gravitational influences, challenges traditional notions of resistance and trajectory. In this context, the exploration of volition prompts speculation on whether consciousness, if capable of independent movement, would adhere to conventional notions of spatial orientation or if it would manifest in a more fluid and multidimensional manner. The cosmic canvas thus becomes a backdrop for examining the interplay between the ethereal nature of consciousness, as posited by spiritual traditions, and the physical realities of the cosmic expanse. The integration of these perspectives contributes to a holistic exploration of

volition, encouraging a dialogue that bridges the realms of metaphysics and astrophysics.

The consideration of factors such as the absence of gravity and the inherent characteristics of the cosmos becomes pivotal when contemplating the plausibility of volition within outer space. In the microgravity environment of space, where gravitational forces are markedly reduced, traditional biomechanics and Newtonian physics give way to the peculiar dynamics of weightlessness. From a scientific perspective, the absence of gravitational constraints raises intriguing questions about the potential manifestation of volition or autonomous movement of consciousness. In this context, the dynamics of volition might be envisaged as decoupled from the familiar physical constraints observed on Earth, presenting an opportunity for consciousness to navigate space without adherence to conventional principles of motion.

Moreover, the characteristics of the cosmos, marked by vast distances, celestial bodies, and cosmic phenomena, introduce an additional layer of complexity to the contemplation of volition in space. The sheer scale of the universe challenges the traditional notions of spatial navigation and prompts considerations about the scope and reach of consciousness. The interplay between the purported capacities of volition and the cosmic expanse beckons exploration into how consciousness might interact with and traverse astronomical distances. The absence of an atmospheric medium and the unique gravitational conditions within space pose both challenges and opportunities for the conceptualization of volition, encouraging a multidisciplinary dialogue between spiritual philosophy and the intricacies of astrophysics.

Speculating on how spiritual experiences during volition might be influenced by the vastness of space involves a consideration of both psychological and metaphysical factors. The expansive cosmic backdrop may shape the perceptual and cognitive aspects of spiritual encounters, potentially enhancing or altering the nature of consciousness during volitional movements. The psychological impact of the cosmic environment could be profound, with the absence of familiar terrestrial references and the exposure to cosmic vastness potentially leading to heightened states of awe, transcendence, or a redefinition of spatial and temporal perceptions. Understanding the interplay

between the psyche and the vastness of space is crucial in unraveling how spiritual experiences unfold during volition, providing insights into the potential transformative effects of cosmic surroundings on the consciousness navigating these ethereal journeys.

Metaphysically, the immensity of space introduces the notion of traversing celestial distances and encountering diverse cosmic phenomena during volitional experiences. Spiritual traditions often postulate that consciousness, in a state of volition, may transcend the limitations of physical boundaries, exploring dimensions beyond the terrestrial realm. The cosmic expanse becomes a canvas for the manifestation of metaphysical principles, where the consciousness engaging in volition is purportedly exposed to celestial energies, planetary influences, and perhaps even encounters with other spiritual entities. The speculative exploration of these metaphysical aspects invites a nuanced examination of how the enormity of space contributes to the richness and complexity of spiritual experiences, fueling a discourse that integrates both the cosmic and spiritual dimensions of volition.

The discussion of spiritual perception in a cosmic environment involves exploring the interface between metaphysical concepts and sensory perception. Spiritual traditions posit that consciousness, detached from the physical body, perceives the environment through a non-physical lens, influenced by celestial energies and vibrational frequencies (F., 1964). This non-physical mode of perception raises questions about the nature of non-material cognition in an extraterrestrial setting (Dresler et al., 2014). The challenge lies in elucidating how such spiritual perception aligns with or deviates from the established understanding of sensory modalities.

In the context of volition within the cosmic expanse, the study of volitional components of consciousness across wakefulness, dreaming, and lucid dreaming is crucial (Dresler et al., 2014). Volitional components of consciousness vary across these states, and understanding this variation is essential in the exploration of spiritual perception in a cosmic environment. Additionally, consciousness is considered as the temporal propagation of information from the past to the future, providing a framework to understand subjective experience through information theory (Revach & Salti, 2022).

The presence of amino acids and biomarkers in extraterrestrial materials has implications for the potential existence of extraterrestrial life (Georgiou, 2018; Parker et al., 2022). The functional properties of amino acid side chains serve as biomarkers of extraterrestrial life, indicating the possibility of life originating within volume/space-constrained compartments containing chemical reactions catalyzed by certain polymers (Georgiou, 2018). Additionally, the identification of non-protein amino acids in carbon-rich meteorite particles suggests the potential for the existence of organic compounds in extraterrestrial materials (Parker et al., 2022).

Moreover, the study of spiritual care competence and perceptions among nurses is relevant in understanding the role of spirituality in healthcare settings (Kang et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2022). Nurses' perceptions of spirituality and spiritual care are essential in creating spiritually conducive environments that improve patient, nurse, and organizational outcomes (Cruz et al., 2018). Understanding the perceptions of spiritual care among healthcare professionals is crucial in addressing the spiritual needs of individuals in a cosmic environment.

The exploration of spiritual perception in a cosmic environment requires an interdisciplinary approach that integrates metaphysical concepts, sensory modalities, consciousness, and the potential existence of extraterrestrial life. Understanding the nature of non-material cognition, the presence of biomarkers in extraterrestrial materials, and the role of spirituality in healthcare settings are essential in addressing the complex questions raised by spiritual traditions in the context of the cosmic expanse.

Furthermore, the discussion extends to the potential effects of the cosmic environment on the spiritual consciousness engaged in volition. Scientifically, the lack of a conventional sensory apparatus, such as eyes or ears, poses intriguing inquiries into the mechanisms by which consciousness might perceive and interpret the cosmic surroundings. The cosmic arena introduces unique challenges and possibilities for spiritual perception, including the absence of traditional reference points, the exposure to celestial phenomena, and the potential for encounters with spiritual entities. Navigating these uncharted metaphysical territories invites a nuanced dialogue between

spiritual philosophy and the scientific understanding of consciousness, pushing the boundaries of how we conceptualize perception in the cosmic context.

The consideration of alternative perspectives on volition in space demands a critical examination of dissenting views within scientific and philosophical discourses. From a skeptical scientific standpoint, alternative explanations might be sought within the realm of neurobiology or altered states of consciousness rather than attributing the observed phenomena to metaphysical causes. Skeptics may propose that purported volitional experiences in space are manifestations of neurological processes, such as lucid dreaming or hallucinations, triggered by unique conditions in the cosmic environment. In this line of reasoning, the focus shifts from metaphysical interpretations to exploring the neurophysiological underpinnings of the reported phenomena, calling for empirical scrutiny and systematic investigations into the potential cognitive effects of the space environment on human consciousness.

Philosophically, alternative perspectives may emerge from diverse spiritual or cultural traditions that offer contrasting explanations for experiences resembling volition in space. Each tradition may provide its own cosmological framework, shaping how the phenomenon is interpreted and understood. These alternative viewpoints may present distinct ontologies, challenging the assumptions inherent in the Spiritist and Conscienciological perspectives. A comprehensive exploration of these alternatives involves delving into the cultural, historical, and religious contexts that underpin such divergent views, fostering a nuanced understanding of the multifaceted nature of the discourse surrounding volition in the cosmic realm. Engaging with these alternative perspectives enriches the dialogue, encouraging a more comprehensive and inclusive examination of the phenomenon across different intellectual and cultural paradigms.

A critical analysis and comparison of perspectives within and outside the Spiritist and Conscienciological traditions necessitate a rigorous examination of the underlying assumptions, methodologies, and empirical evidence supporting these viewpoints. Within these spiritual traditions, the emphasis is often on personal experiences, mediumistic communications, and anecdotal evidence, which may lack the scientific rigor required for broad acceptance. The challenge lies in reconciling the metaphysical claims of volition

with the empirical standards upheld by the scientific community. Skeptics may contend that the subjective nature of spiritual experiences makes them inherently challenging to validate or reproduce, emphasizing the need for controlled studies that adhere to scientific methodologies. Comparative analysis demands an evaluation of the epistemological foundations, highlighting both the convergences and divergences between these spiritual perspectives and the methodologies endorsed by mainstream scientific inquiry.

Beyond these traditions, alternative perspectives may offer contrasting epistemologies and interpretative frameworks. Scientific disciplines such as psychology and neuroscience may approach the phenomenon of volition through the lens of brain function, cognitive processes, or altered states of consciousness. The critical analysis involves assessing the methodological soundness of these approaches, considering the limitations of reductionist paradigms, and acknowledging the potential blind spots in solely materialistic interpretations. A comprehensive comparison of these perspectives necessitates an interdisciplinary approach that acknowledges the strengths and limitations of each, fostering a dialogue that seeks to bridge the gaps between spiritual and scientific worldviews. Such a critical analysis is fundamental for advancing our understanding of volition and its place within the broader context of human consciousness and the cosmos.

The contemplation of volition in space is accompanied by a myriad of potential challenges, spanning the realms of logic, science, and ethics. From a logical perspective, the very concept of volition implies a form of movement that defies the laws of physics as we currently understand them. The absence of a conventional propulsion system or a comprehensible mechanism for autonomous movement raises fundamental questions about the coherence of the proposed phenomenon. Logical challenges also extend to the definition and measurement of volition, as its subjective and metaphysical nature complicates attempts to establish standardized criteria for its observation and verification. Addressing these logical challenges requires a nuanced evaluation of the assumptions underlying the concept of volition, scrutinizing its compatibility with established scientific principles and logical coherence.

Scientifically, the idea of volition in space encounters challenges related to empirical validation and the reproducibility of reported experiences.

The lack of a standardized methodology for studying metaphysical phenomena, coupled with the inherently subjective nature of spiritual experiences, poses obstacles to scientific scrutiny. Additionally, the dearth of consensus on the operational definition of volition hampers the formulation of testable hypotheses and the design of controlled experiments. The scientific community faces the ethical dilemma of balancing the exploration of unconventional phenomena with the rigor demanded by the scientific method, ensuring that investigations into volition consider the potential biases, ethical implications, and methodological constraints inherent in the study of spiritual and metaphysical phenomena. These challenges necessitate a collaborative effort between scientists, philosophers, and spiritual practitioners to navigate the intricate intersections of logic, science, and ethics surrounding the concept of volition in the cosmic domain.

External criticisms directed at the traditions exploring volition in space often emanate from scientific, philosophical, and cultural standpoints. From a scientific perspective, the lack of empirical evidence supporting the claims of volition poses a significant challenge. Critics argue that the reliance on anecdotal accounts, subjective experiences, and mediumistic communications within these traditions falls short of the rigorous standards demanded by the scientific method. The absence of controlled experiments, standardized measurement protocols, and reproducible results raises skepticism among those who adhere strictly to the empirical criteria of scientific inquiry. Moreover, external critics may contend that the concepts of volition and spiritual consciousness lack operational definitions that would enable consistent evaluation, making it difficult to subject these phenomena to systematic investigation.

Philosophically, external criticisms often center around the epistemological foundations of these spiritual traditions. Critics may question the coherence of metaphysical constructs like the perispirit or consciencial energies, demanding a clearer articulation of these concepts within a broader philosophical framework. Cultural and religious biases may also contribute to external criticisms, as individuals from different philosophical or belief systems may interpret the phenomena of volition through their own cultural lenses, leading to divergent perspectives and critiques. Addressing external criticisms

necessitates a willingness within these traditions to engage in interdisciplinary dialogue, incorporating insights from philosophy, psychology, and the natural sciences to refine their conceptual frameworks and enhance the credibility of their claims in the eyes of external observers.

In summary, this article delves into the exploration of volition within the context of Spiritism and Conscienciology, two spiritual traditions that posit the existence of metaphysical phenomena such as out-of-body experiences and autonomous movement of consciousness. Grounded in the teachings of Allan Kardec and Waldo Vieira, these traditions propose that volition allows the spirit or consciousness to navigate space independently of the physical body, raising intriguing questions about the interplay between metaphysical claims and empirical scrutiny. The article critically examines the theoretical foundations, explores reported cases, and contemplates the potential implications of volition within the cosmic expanse, considering factors such as the absence of gravity and the characteristics of the cosmos.

The inquiry extends to the philosophical and scientific challenges associated with volition in space, acknowledging potential logical, methodological, and ethical dilemmas. Additionally, the article considers external criticisms from scientific and cultural perspectives, emphasizing the need for an interdisciplinary dialogue that bridges the gap between spiritual and scientific worldviews. By navigating through these intricate intersections, this exploration seeks to foster a comprehensive understanding of volition within the cosmic domain, acknowledging the complexities inherent in reconciling spiritual doctrines with empirical rigor while encouraging a nuanced discourse that enriches both realms of inquiry.

Highlighting areas that warrant further research and contemplation within the exploration of volition in space is essential for advancing both scientific and spiritual understandings. First and foremost, a critical need exists for systematic and controlled studies that investigate the purported metaphysical phenomena, such as volition, in a rigorous scientific manner. The development of standardized protocols for studying consciousness in altered states and the establishment of criteria for defining and measuring volitional experiences are crucial steps toward achieving empirical clarity. Collaborative efforts between scientists, spiritual practitioners, and philosophers are

imperative to design experiments that address the inherent challenges of studying non-material consciousness within the cosmic context, fostering a more cohesive integration of metaphysical claims with empirical methodologies.

Furthermore, the articulation and refinement of theoretical frameworks within Spiritism and Conscienciology are areas that demand focused attention. A more precise delineation of terms, such as perispirit and consciencial energies, and a rigorous exploration of their metaphysical implications are necessary for bolstering the conceptual foundations of these traditions. This involves engaging with interdisciplinary perspectives, incorporating insights from philosophy of mind, neuroscience, and psychology to enhance the explanatory power of these frameworks. By addressing these avenues for further inquiry, researchers and practitioners can contribute to a more nuanced and informed discourse, establishing a solid foundation for future investigations into the nature of consciousness and volition within the expansive backdrop of cosmic environments.

Inviting readers to reflect on the presented exploration of volition within the cosmic domain is an invitation to engage in a contemplative examination at the intersection of spirituality and scientific inquiry. The inherent complexities and unanswered questions surrounding the phenomena discussed prompt readers to consider the implications of reconciling metaphysical claims with the rigorous standards of empirical scrutiny. Encouraging a critical evaluation of the evidence, readers are prompted to assess the validity and reliability of reported cases, the theoretical frameworks within spiritual traditions, and the potential avenues for interdisciplinary collaboration between scientific and spiritual communities.

Moreover, this reflection invites readers to contemplate the broader implications of exploring consciousness and volition in the context of space. The convergence of spiritual doctrines and astrophysical realities raises profound questions about the nature of human consciousness, the limits of scientific methodologies, and the intricate relationship between the mind and the cosmos. As readers navigate through the intricacies of this discourse, they are urged to contribute to an ongoing dialogue that seeks to transcend disciplinary boundaries, fostering a more comprehensive understanding of consciousness, spirituality, and the potential for volition in the vastness of the cosmic realm.

This reflective engagement serves as an intellectual catalyst for continued inquiry, challenging readers to delve deeper into the enigmatic intersections between the metaphysical and the empirical.

3. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

In concluding our exploration of volition within the frameworks of Spiritism and Conscientiology, the intricate interplay between spiritual philosophy, metaphysical phenomena, and empirical inquiry becomes increasingly apparent. The theoretical foundations presented by Allan Kardec and Waldo Vieira serve as gateways to understanding consciousness, its autonomy, and its potential interactions with the cosmic expanse.

As we traverse the metaphysical landscapes of levitation and volition, the call for systematic and controlled studies echoes prominently. The need for standardized protocols and interdisciplinary collaboration becomes imperative to bridge the gap between spiritual claims and scientific scrutiny. Our journey through reported cases and theoretical frameworks emphasizes the challenges inherent in reconciling metaphysical phenomena with empirical standards, urging a harmonious integration of diverse perspectives.

The contemplation of volition in space invites us to reflect not only on the vastness of the cosmos but also on the potential transformative effects of the cosmic environment on consciousness. The absence of familiar terrestrial references and exposure to cosmic vastness may reshape spiritual experiences, challenging our understanding of perception, cognition, and the very nature of volitional movements.

Acknowledging external criticisms and alternative perspectives enriches the discourse, highlighting the need for a comprehensive and inclusive examination of the phenomenon across different intellectual and cultural paradigms. The dialogue between spiritual and scientific worldviews requires ongoing reflection, fostering mutual understanding, and encouraging a collective pursuit of knowledge.

In these final considerations, we recognize that the exploration of volition within the cosmic domain is an ongoing journey. It beckons researchers, practitioners, and seekers to delve deeper into the enigmatic intersections between the metaphysical and the empirical. By navigating through the

complexities and unanswered questions, we contribute to a holistic understanding of consciousness, spirituality, and the potential for volition in the boundless expanse of the cosmos.

REFERENCES

- | |
|--|
| <p>Cruz, J., Alquwez, N., Albaqawi, H., Alharbi, S., & Moreno-Lacalle, R. (2018). Nurses' perceived spiritual climate of a hospital in Saudi Arabia. <i>International Nursing Review</i>, 65(4), 559-566. https://doi.org/10.1111/inr.12481</p> |
| <p>Dresler, M., Eibl, L., Fischer, C., Wehrle, R., Spoomaker, V., Steiger, A., ... & Pawlowski, M. (2014). Volitional components of consciousness vary across wakefulness, dreaming and lucid dreaming. <i>Frontiers in Psychology</i>, 4. https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2013.00987</p> |
| <p>F., C. (1964). The varieties of religious experience. <i>American Journal of Psychiatry</i>, 120(12), 1211-1212. https://doi.org/10.1176/ajp.120.12.1211</p> |
| <p>Georgiou, C. (2018). Functional properties of amino acid side chains as biomarkers of extraterrestrial life. <i>Astrobiology</i>, 18(11), 1479-1496. https://doi.org/10.1089/ast.2018.1868</p> |
| <p>Kang, K., Chun, J., Yong, K., & Kim, H. (2021). Hospice palliative care nurses' perceptions of spiritual care and their spiritual care competence: a mixed-methods study. <i>Journal of Clinical Nursing</i>, 30(7-8), 961-974. https://doi.org/10.1111/jocn.15638</p> |
| <p>Parker, E., Chan, Q., Glavin, D., & Dworkin, J. (2022). Non-protein amino acids identified in carbon-rich Hayabusa particles. <i>Meteoritics and Planetary Science</i>, 57(4), 776-793. https://doi.org/10.1111/maps.13794</p> |
| <p>Revach, D. and Salti, M. (2022). Consciousness as the temporal propagation of information. <i>Frontiers in Systems Neuroscience</i>, 16. https://doi.org/10.3389/fnsys.2022.759683</p> |
| <p>Wang, Z., Zhao, H., Zhang, S., Wang, Y., Zhang, Y., Wang, Z., ... & Pang, X. (2022). Correlations among spiritual care competence, spiritual care perceptions and spiritual health of Chinese nurses: a cross-sectional correlational study. <i>Palliative & Supportive Care</i>, 20(2), 243-254. https://doi.org/10.1017/s1478951521001966</p> |